

Entropy, Identity in Terms of Interaction and Gibbs Paradox

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Boltzmann entropy is defined as $-k \ln(\text{number of macrostates})$. A macrostate, however, is composed of many particles which have certain physical attributes. The question then becomes: Are all physical attributes important in calculating the number of macrostates? For instance, if one could, for the sake of argument, have a different colour for each particle, would different colour arrangements with the same spatial and momentum distributions represent different macrostates? We argue that they would not because as we have argued in a previous note, the maximization of entropy is really linked to two particle scattering in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, i.e. the particular interaction in question. In other words, we argue that different macrostates are created by considering only the attributes which are associated with different possible interactions. Having a red or green ball with momentum p at x has nothing to do with different interactions. The interactions are the key feature as the Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy which is consistent with the first law of thermodynamics entropy is linked with changes in energy and work which deal with interactions. Thus, we suggest that one must be careful in considering what macrostates lead to different possible interactions and which do not. We suggest that this is why one divides the number of states by $N!$ to eliminate Gibbs' paradox. The rearrangement of particles has no effect on the interactions possible for a given macrostate configuration. One might ask: Why does one consider the identity for N particles in the first place? In Newtonian mechanics, one follows each particle through $x(t)$ and two particles cannot be at the same x at the same time. Thus, in Newtonian mechanics each particle has a distinct identity. In classical statistical mechanics, however, we argue that it is the macrostates linked with different interaction schemes which are to be considered.

Boltzmann Entropy

Boltzmann entropy is defined as:

$$S = -k \ln(\text{number of macrostates}) \quad ((1))$$

A macrostate consists of a number of particles with attributes which may or may not contribute to different macrostates. For example, if one could, for the sake of argument, have a different colour for each particle, then given a certain configuration with particles at $\{r_i\}$ where r_i is an r vector for particle i and $\{p_i\}$, where p_i is a momentum vector for particle i , can one create new macrostates by interchanging the colour of the particles? Certainly these are different physical states, but based on what measurement criteria? We suggest that macrostates must be distinguished on the basis of possible interactions. Thus, different momenta at different r positions suggest different possible interactions, but colour has nothing to do with interactions and it is irrelevant, from the point of view of interaction, whether one has a green particle or red one at r with momentum p .

Why Are Configurations Associated with Interactions Key?

We argue that only macrostates related to different interactions are key for two reasons. First, the Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy appears in the first law of thermodynamics;

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((2))$$

Two terms in this equation are linked with interaction, namely dE and PdV . We thus suggest that dS should also be linked with interactions. Changing a red ball to a green one does not change E and is not linked with work, but it would change dS if one considers any physical attribute as changing a macrostate.

A second reason is that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained without the use of entropy, by considering two body elastic scattering, i.e.

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((3b))$$

One may take \ln of ((3b)) and equate to ((3a)) multiplied by $-1/T$. T may then be fixed through:

$$\sum_i e_i C \exp(-e_i/T) = E_{ave} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, we suggest that entropy as $\ln(\text{number of macrostates})$ must be considered within an interaction context and one cannot consider different states which represent exactly the same interaction scheme, i.e. interchanging colour for example.

Gibbs Paradox

Gibbs paradox is solved by dividing the number of classical phase space states by $N!$, (i.e. the term V^N where N is the number of particles). It is often stated that this is done because in quantum mechanics particles are said to be identical. We suggest that it is really done because if one has a set of N particles with a particular $\{r_i\}$, $\{p_i\}$ configuration, then interchanging the identity of the particles does not change the interaction scheme.

This begs the question: Why would each of the N particles have its own identity? In Newtonian mechanics, each particle is followed by $x(t)$. If two particles cannot be at the same x at the same t , then each particle has a distinct identity in Newtonian mechanics. In classical statistical mechanics, one drops t so one no longer follows a particle through $x(t)$, but the notion of an identity is carried over from the Newtonian picture.

If, however, a macrostate is defined as a scheme representing possible interactions, then particle identity is no longer a consideration as argued above using colour. One only considers possible interaction schemes.

Entropy and Different Interaction Schemes

We argued above that the number of macrostates depends on different interaction configurations, not simply on different physical states. It is possible, however, to have different interactions in a problem. For example, one may have probabilities for a set of particles all with the same momentum, but different velocities. If one is not considered with time, but only with the impact on a target, all of these p are the same and one has no probability in the problem. If, on the other hand, one is concerned with velocities (or kinetic energies) one may create a Shannon's entropy using these. Similarly, a die has six numbers and one may create an informational Shannon's entropy using $P=1/6$, but in terms of energy, all states with a face up have the same energy. Thus, in terms of an energy equation the six sides up are degenerate states.

If one considers a quantum free particle it has a momentum, but also a wavelength. If one is only interested in target impulses, then only information about p is needed and the resolution \hbar/p is not of interest. If, on the other hand, one has 2-slits with various separations, then $\exp(ipx)$ becomes relevant and one has an entropy linked to this.

Thus, we suggest that entropy, or number of states, is related to the particular interactions of concern, rather than being a universal concept.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Boltzmann definition of entropy $-k \ln(\text{number of macrostates})$ begs the question as to the meaning of a macrostate. Is it a configuration of single particle attributes which differs from another configuration? We argue that this is not the case. We suggest that a macrostate represents a configuration representing a unique interaction scheme. Thus, if one has attributes, such as colour, which have nothing to do with interactions then interchanging colours does not create a new macrostate. In particular, we note that in Newtonian mechanics each particle has a distinct identity because $x(t)$ means that one cannot have two particles at the same x and t . This distinct particle identity carries over into classical statistical mechanics in which time is dropped. Even though each particle may be distinct in some way, it is not distinct in terms of interactions. One only wishes to have macrostates which represent different interaction schemes. Thus, one cannot overcount macrostates by considering different arrangements of N particles and so divides the number of states by $N!$ to resolve the Gibbs paradox.